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M. Regueiro, G. García-Alén, J. Naves, E. Sañudo, L. Cea, S. Puertas, G. Vila, L. Pena, J. Puertas

URBAN FLOOD ANALYSIS USING HYBRID PHYSICAL-DIGITAL TWINS WITH VIRTUAL WATER: A TOOL FOR DISSEMINATING RESULTS TO NON-TECHNICAL STAKEHOLDERS.

The management of floods in urban areas requires the participation of various stakeholders and agencies, some of which do not have a technical background. Disaster management authorities, municipalities and, above all, the potentially affected population are important players in flood management, and their awareness and understanding of the phenomena is a vital activity.

Flood calculation models in urban areas are becoming increasingly complex. Many countries already have a DTM whose detail allows a realistic representation of the land surface, including buildings and streets, and, although not always, it is also common to have a detailed understanding of the drainage and sewerage network. This allows the models to provide a reasonably accurate representation of flood risk, but the calculation process is complex, which leads to some difficulty in disseminating the information to stakeholders.

The infrastructure presented in this paper allows to reproduce in real time the whole calculation on an urban surface, in an immersive environment, very easy to understand by non-technical stakeholders. It is a hybrid technology that seeks to take advantage of the benefits of physical and numerical modeling.

The components of the infrastructure are 1.- a physical scale model, 2.- a LiDAR probe, which allows a real time reading of the model geometry, 3.- a real time calculation model, which in this case is 2D Iber model, with a calculation mesh adapted to the dimensions of the model and a simplified and friendly method of introducing the parameters, and 4.- a system of projection of the model results by means of "virtual water".

This infrastructure has been applied to a specific case, in the town of Sada (Spain), traditionally affected by floods. The urban geometry has been obtained from a DTM, and has been reproduced to scale in a physical model by 3D printing. The calculations are and projected in real time. The advantage over a conventional calculation is that the whole process is much more visual, intelligible and understandable to a non-technical audience, and that improvements or solutions can be implemented directly on the model, directly by changing parts in the model instantaneously, and their effect can be observed immediately.

Being able to observe the effect of floods and how to mitigate them in an immersive and realistic way allows discussion among stakeholders, who understand the solutions and come to trust them, which then allows their actual implementation with a high degree of consensus.